

Influence of CaO/SiO₂ Ratio and Storage Conditions of CaO on Silica-Lime-Water System under Hydrothermal Treatment

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The effect of CaO/SiO₂ ratio from 0.08 to 1.6 and the storage conditions of CaO in open atmosphere for 1–28 days have been investigated. The optimum C/S ratio at which maximum strength and complete consumption of CaO in the reaction occur, is 0.11. Increasing the CaO content beyond this ratio leads to the formation of lime-rich calcium silicate hydrate, with low strength. The results of storage conditions of lime indicate that during the first three days the reaction between CaO and atmospheric moisture reaches its maximum, while the reaction of CaO with atmospheric CO₂ does not occur to appreciable extent. After that period, the slaked CaO reacts rapidly with the atmospheric CO₂ forming CaCO₃.

The strength of the autoclaved sand-lime products increases almost proportionally with the lime content up to the point at which the available surface of the silica is insufficient to maintain this relation, and strength then increases more slowly up to a maximum beyond which the strength falls with further increase of the lime content¹. Bessy and Purton², found that the lime content for maximum strength may be as low as 5% with the coarsest mixes and as high as 40% with a linear range from zero to 30% with finely ground silica. The relationship between the strength and lime/silica ratio for silica having different specific surface area was investigated³. It was shown that for each grade of silica flour there is a certain lime/silica ratio at which the compressive strength is maximum. Gundlach *et al.*⁴ found that the optimum CaO content for producing sand-lime brick can be calculated from the following equation,

$$\% \text{CaO}_{\text{opt}} = 4.3 \times 10^{-3} \cdot O_{\text{sp}} \text{ (of quartz)} + 12.5$$

where the specific surface area of quartz (O_{sp}) is determined in cm²/g after Blaine. This equation is applied only for quartz with surface area more than 1000 cm²/g. Recently it has been reported⁵ that the increase in the Ca/Si ratio leads to a morphological changes in the binder, CSH (calcium silicate hydrate) phases, from microbead-like crystals to slightly spherical particles accompanied by strength decrease.

The quality of the lime used is a major consideration in calcium silicate brick manufacture: it depends upon the composition and nature of the stone used, the conditions of burning and specific surface area of lime⁶. Magnesia in lime is liable to hydration in autoclave and causes expansion. Therefore its amount must be limited; for example, in United Kingdom, 5% may be tolerated⁷. In burning limestone, CO₂ is released which constitutes up to 44% of its weight, but the volume of the product decreases by about 10%, which means that lump quicklime has a porous structure⁸ with a high affinity for moisture and hydration.

Results and Discussion

The lime content :

The results indicate that for a given sand grading the compressive strength increases with increasing the lime content until it reaches the optimum strength (366 kg/cm²) at lime-sand ratio of 0.11 by weight, beyond which a reduction in strength was observed with increasing lime content up to 16%. The apparent porosity decreases continuously with increasing amount of lime up to 12.5%, then increases with further increase of the lime content. The bulk density increases with the increase of lime content up to 11%, and further increase of lime is associated with a sharp decrease in the bulk density.

The results of free lime determination are graphically presented as a function of the lime content in the starting mix in Fig. 1. The free lime increases at a slow rate, up to 11% lime content. Further increase in the lime content is

Fig. 1. Influence of mixing lime content on the free lime of the products.

associated with a sharp increase in the free lime to reach 2.74% with lime content of 16%. The change in physico-mechanical properties as a function of lime content in the starting mix can be explained on the basis of the amount and sort of the formed hydration products and on the

amount of unreacted lime (free lime). With increasing lime content in the original mix from 8 to 11%, nearly all the lime found enough available silicate ions to react with, so the amounts of hydration products increase with increasing the lime content up to 11%. The precipitation of the hydration products in the pore system of the specimens bind the sand grains together, so the porosity decreases and accordingly the strength increases. This is accompanied by the slow increase in the free lime content, to reach 0.6% at the initial lime content of 11% (Fig. 1). This small amount of free lime may be due to some possible errors, since the solvent mixture used for the determination of free lime mentioned before could attack the lime-rich calcium hydrosilicate (amorphous calcium hydrosilicates) and leach some of the lime which results in the detection of this small value of free lime.

With increasing lime content in the starting mix beyond 11%, the excess lime could not find enough available silicate ions under the experimental conditions. So lime-rich phases are formed, which are associated with lower strength values and lower bulk density⁹. Some lime stays in free state, which dilutes the bond between particles, resulting also in the strength decrease and in the porosity increase.

Storage conditions of lime :

Rate of carbonation and hydration of lime : The phase composition of stored lime at different storage times has been studied. During the first 3 days of storage, the rate of hydration (air slaking) reaches a maximum, but the carbonation does not occur to any appreciable extent until hydration of CaO is nearly complete (after 3 days). In the third day of storage, the amount of Ca(OH)₂ reached 86.7%, then the hydrated lime starts converting into carbonate, so the percent of carbonate is increased and Ca(OH)₂ decreased. During the time interval 3–8 days, the carbonation increases progressively. At the end of 8 days, nearly no CaO is present, and this depends to a fair extent on the particle size of the lime and on the degree of humidity of air. During 8–18 days, the rate of carbonation starts to slow down, since carbonation starts first on the grain surface upon which a shell of calcium carbonate is gradually formed. As the CaCO₃ accumulates, densification occurs, thus making it more difficult for CO₂ to penetrate through narrow pores to combine with interior CaO or Ca(OH)₂ molecules.

After 18 days, the carbonation nearly stops at a carbonate percent of 58%, since the complete carbonation does not occur as the carbonate densification accumulates to form a carbonate crust around lime grains; the carbonation is totally stopped down at a certain percent which depends on the particle size of lime and humidity of air. Larger lime grains recarbonate at a lower rate. These results are in a good agreement with that reported by Song and Kim¹⁰ in which they showed that the formed calcium carbonate film on CaO or Ca(OH)₂ surface makes protective layer and prevents further carbonation. At this stage, the carbonation reaction is totally diffusion-controlled.

Available lime content : The active lime (available lime) was calculated from the chemical analysis and estimated by the rapid sugar test¹¹. In general, the results show that the contents of active lime estimated by sugar test are usually 2–6% less than the calculated total CaO. Active lime decreases with the progress of storage time. In the first 8 days, it shows a sharp decrease due to the conversion of CaO and/or Ca(OH)₂ into CaCO₃. After 8 days, the available CaO shows a slow decrease. During the time period 18–28 days, the available lime reaches a constant value (29.7–29.3%) since the carbonation is stopped.

Sand-lime samples prepared with stored lime :

The physico-mechanical properties of sand-lime brick samples prepared with lime stored for different times (1, 3, 8, 18 and 28 days) at room conditions are given as a function of storage time in Fig. 2. Generally, the data show that the compressive strength can be correlated with the amount of the available lime. Thus the strength is constant for

Fig. 2. Effect of storage time of lime on the physico-mechanical properties of SL-bricks.

samples which were prepared with lime stored for zero, 1 and 3 days respectively. After, 3 days, the strength decreases, so much as the storage time is increased (or as the available lime decreased), to reach a constant value during 18–28 days. The porosity of the samples decreases

Fig. 3. Effect of storage time of lime on combined water and C/S molar ratio of sand-lime products.

with increasing storage time of lime up to 3 days, then increases again with further increase of storage time. The bulk density follows the reverse trend.

The results show that the free lime decreases with the elongation of storage time to reach zero from storage time

longer than 18 days. The free silica value increases continuously with increasing storage time of lime. The combined lime and combined silica show continuous decrease with increasing storage time to reach constant values at storage times from 18 to 28 days.

The chemically combined water and the molar C/S ratio of the binder were calculated after making the necessary corrections. The results presented as a function of storage time of lime (Fig. 3) show decrease in both the chemically combined water and the C/S molar ratio of the binder with the prolongation of storage time of the used lime. This decrease confirms a lowering in the amount of the formed calcium silicate hydrate which is characterized by a low lime content due to the decrease in the available lime.

The autoclaved samples M₁, M₂, M₃ and M₄ respectively of storage times of zero, 1, 3 and 18 days were examined by X-ray diffraction. The results are in a good agreement with those of the chemical analysis, since the free lime appears clearly for sample M₁ and it could not be detected in the other samples. The intensity of the peaks characterizing CaCO₃ increases as the storage time of lime is increased. No CaCO₃ could be detected in the control sample (M₁), but appears as traces in sample M₂. However, it becomes detectable for sample M₃ and reaches its maximum for sample M₄. These results are in harmony with the carbonate content of the used lime. The X-ray diffraction patterns show that tobermorite appears only as traces for the control sample (M₁), as indicated by its characteristic peaks at 3.07 and 11.3 Å. The intensities increased in sharpness with increasing storage time of lime up to 3 days (sample M₃). For sample M₄, tobermorite is seen, with peaks of lower sharpness than those of sample M₃.

The physico-mechanical properties, kinetics of hydration and phase composition of the hardened specimens, can be related to the amounts of available CaO, and the degree of carbonation of the used lime in the starting mix. As the storage time is increased, the available lime content decreases. This is mainly due to the hydration process during the first 3 days, followed by the carbonation reaction. XRD analysis as well as the continuous decrease in the C/S molar ratio of the binder calculated from the results of chemical analysis (Fig. 3) are as expected, since decreasing initial bulk C/S ratio of the raw mix causes the consumption of lime in shorter autoclaving time. Increasing the storage time of lime beyond 3 days causes a sharp decrease in the compressive strength of the final products, in effect decreasing the amount of the formed calcium hydrosilicates.

Experimental

In this work natural sand from El-Abbassa sand-lime Brick Co., Egypt was used. Its chemical analysis and grain size distribution are given in Table 1.

Lime, CaO, was prepared by firing analytical grade CaCO₃ at 1000° for 1.5 h. For obtaining the optimum CaO/SiO₂ ratio, sand-lime mixes were prepared using C/S ratios from 0.08 to 0.16 by weight and 13% H₂O, pressed in a cylindrical form (2 cm dia × 3 cm). The samples were then autoclaved at 10 bar for 8 h. For studying the effect of storage conditions, the CaO was spread in 1.5 cm layer thick in a porcelain dish at room temperature in open atmosphere from 1 to 28 days. The active lime¹¹, the rate of

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL ANALYSIS AND PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION OF USED SAND

Chemical analysis		Particle size distribution	
Component	wt. %	Size (mm)	wt. %
SiO ₂	97.90	2.00–1.00	5.60
Al ₂ O ₃	1.30	1.00–0.71	10.00
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.20	0.71–0.50	18.80
CaO+MgO	0.17	0.50–0.25	37.70
K ₂ O+Na ₂ O	0.22	0.25–0.125	17.90
SO ₃	0.06	0.125–0.063	3.40
Cl	0.10	0.063	6.60
L.O.I.	0.30		

air slaking and atmospheric carbonation were measured. The exposed lime was employed in the preparation of sand-lime samples. Sand-lime mixes were prepared using the optimum C/S ratio of 0.11. The rate of reaction was followed by determining the chemically combined water, unreacted Ca(OH)₂ and reacted SiO₂. The C/S molar ratio as well as the amount of the reaction products were calculated. The phase composition was investigated by XRD. In addition, the physico-mechanical properties were also studied.

References

1. G. E. BESSEY in "Chemistry of Cement" ed. H. F. W. TAYLOR, Academic, New York, 1964, Vol. II, Chap. 16, p. 107.
2. G. E. BESSEY and M. J. PURTON, 'Proc. Symp. Auto. Calc. Silic. Build. Prod.', London, 1967, p. 18.
3. L. M. KHAVKIN and R. L. KOVAL, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1978, **89**, 202827; H. F. W. TAYLOR, W. F. COLE, and D. R. MOOREHEAD, *Nature*, 1964, **201**, 918.
4. H. GUNDLACH, E. HORSTER, and G. REDERMACHER, '2nd. Inter. Symp. Aut. Calc. Silic. Bdg. Prod.', Hannover, Preprint, 1969.
5. S. SUZUKI and E. SINN, *J. Mat. Sci. Lett.*, 1994, **13**, 1058.
6. W. OHNEMULLER and B. HUPE, 'Kalk-Sand Sym.', Hannover, 1969, Paper no. 57.
7. B. S. 890, "Building Limes", Br. Standrads Inst., London, 1972.
8. A. KOMAR, "Building Materials and Components", Mir Publishers, Moscow, 1974.
9. H. F. W. TAYLOR, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 1986, **69**, 464.
10. H. S. SONG and H. KIM, *Cement Concrete Res.*, 1990, **20**, 815.
11. R. S. BOYNTON, "Chemistry and Technology of Lime and Limestone", 2nd ed., Wiley, New York, 1980, Chap. 7.